

THE PROBLEMS OF LINGUISTIC COMPRESSION IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

Usmonjonova Mahliyo Zokirjon qizi

Second-year student of master's degree, Namangan state university

(Teacher in Uchqurgon region school 12)

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Annotation. The article is devoted to the problems of linguistic compression in Modern English and Uzbek. It gives significant information on the investigation of the topic and value of theoretical principles of linguistic compression in world linguistics.

Keywords: phenomenon, compression, notion, self-expression, communication, advertising.

Compression is a very wide notion – it implied different language level transformations starting from the word-level transformations to the transformations of the whole text. Linguistic compression is used overall - in oral and written discourse, in formal and in informal text materials, every year it expands and deepens its sphere of influence. Today compression is widely applied in the language of mass media. Analysing the mass-media sphere we take into consideration different magazines and internet editions, as well as the range of social networks that are quickly becoming the main field for self-expression, communication and advertising. Mass-media is the general resource of new language transformations and new language constructions that subsequently are included in the language corpora. So, we consider social networks as the specific kind of mass media, and on the basis of Internet resources we would make an attempt to identify several ways of compressing the information, grading them by priority (the frequency of use by Internet users)[2].

Considering the intention to make an article actual we base our findings on resources from such social networks as Vkontakte, Instagram, Twitter - the most popular networks of our time (as for the social network Vkontakte - it is the most popular social network in Russia, not in the whole world). The first way to mention should be the most obvious way of linguistic compression that meet the word language level compression. The evidences of wide spreading of such way could be found in every social network. People compress words: instead of «спасибо» they write «спс» in Russian, as well as instead of «thank you» they write «thnx» in English. The second way is breaking the sentence structure - the abundance of incomplete sentences, mass avoiding of punctuation. Interestingly, these features of mass media language are the characteristic of public dialogue and are mostly avoid in the private correspondence [1]. The point is that the audience of these people doesn't look at these messages as at the linguistic phenomenon. We could again stress the fact of the linguistic compression ordinariness. It is worthy to mention that we presented two messages of people who are extremely popular in Russia, especially in social networks, and these people could be considered as the litmus test of the state of modern language, because we could be sure that people follow them and their manners of communication.

Compression is a special type of transformation that is based on the immanent properties of the language system and contributes to bringing extended syntactic constructions to a less complex form, which, however, can transmit the same amount of information as full expanded constructions. Compression in simultaneous translation is traditionally considered in as one of the means of ensuring the very possibility of this type of translation activity and is defined as “saving speech and language means for expressing the same content”.

A.F. Shiryaev defines speech compression as follows: “The method of reducing the volume of a message without causing significant damage to the task that the speaker sets himself is called compression (speech compression)” (p.83). I.V. Poluyan quite rightly notes that, in relation to simultaneous translation, it is hardly possible to talk about compression of the output message, since the output message does not yet exist in its finished form during the operation of a simultaneous interpreter. “One can, however, speak of its design as economical as possible (in terms of the syllable length of its constituent elements)” (p.5). Based on this, compression in simultaneous translation can be considered precisely as an economical design of the output message, providing a decrease in the syllabic value of TT compared to syllabic ST.

In connection with the expansion of the scope of simultaneous translation in the last three decades compared to the previous period of particular relevance was the question of how to implement compression in ST, about the resources of speech compression in translation. Decision this issue would contribute to a significant optimization of the translation process in terms of the time of acceptance of the translation solutions, saving the efforts of translators, improving the quality of translation. This question is also important for didactics of translation: knowledge of possible resources compression in the joint venture and methods for its implementation would allow orient future simultaneous interpreters to develop skills, necessary for the implementation of simultaneous translation in such a way in a manner that prevents the interpreter from lagging too far behind speaker and unreasonable omissions of relevant information and at the same time saves the mental efforts of the translator himself. Among the most important are factor, like the pace of oratorical speech, otherwise called the lack of time. It is quite obvious that it is precisely the "time constraints under fast the pace of the speaker's speech forces the interpreter to bring into the message syntactic and lexical changes in order to reduce volume of text in the target language".

So, the importance compression as a means of implementing the joint venture increases under conditions time deficit. In literature translation, there are no discrepancies between authors in determining the sources and prerequisites of speech compression. G.V. Chernov writes: “Like a reception of simultaneous translation, compression becomes possible due to the redundancy of linguistic means observed in thematic component of the message” (P. 147) agree with him and other researchers. In the most general way compression can be thought of as removing from a message certain redundant elements (however, far from all, because many elements of linguistic redundancy from the text are, in principle, irremovable; every text carries some redundancy). The idea of redundancy of a speech message is the basis for highlighting ways implementation of compression in the ST, which received coverage in special literature.

So, G.V. Chernov proposes to distinguish between syllabic compression (reduction of the syllabic value of the message), syntactic compression (choosing a shorter and simpler syntactic construction compared to some given in the original), lexical compression (expression of the same thought by a smaller number words), semantic compression [3]. In conclusion, speech compression is carried out by synonymous or close to them replacements of phrases and sentences shorter words, phrases and sentences, omitting segments that duplicate the information contained in previous context, omission of semantic units, redundant in a specific situation of communication, and the omission of semantic units, redundant from the point of view of the task of communication.

The overall tendency to brevity and compression that we have observed is not spontaneous; it is reinforced by several characteristics of our time. For example, the industry of on-line computer games is prospering and growing. The huge stake of all games accounts for group games that include interaction between players. As these games are very dynamic (shooters etc) “players should exchange short and informative messages while playing”. Online games are one of the richest sources of compressed words. Despite gamers are the big part of Internet-society, they are only the element in compression developing.

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